

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Evaluation of Neuroprotective Effect of Flax Lignan Against Parkinson's Disease in Animal Model

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 06 Jan. 2025

Keywords:

Parkinson's Disease, Excitatory Amino Acids (EAA's), Neurotoxicity, Neuroprotective, Flax Lignan, 1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine (MPTP), Rotenone.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14606032

ABSTRACT

Parkinson's disease (PD) is likely to increase in the years to come as are related to motor defects such as resting tremor often referred as "pill-rolling", bradykinesia and rigidity of skeletal muscle, postural instability, stooped posture, and freezing of gait. The objective of the present study was to evaluate the neuroprotective activity of natural polyphenols (Flax Lignan) against Parkinson's disease. Evaluation of anti-Parkinson's activity of polyphenols (Flax Lignan) using in-vitro, viz; metal chelation assay, nitric oxide scavenging assays and in-vivo models viz; 1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine (MPTP) mouse model and rotenone model using zebra fish was performed. Various behavioural parameters like, muscle grip strength, locomotor activity, muscle rigidity, complete immobility, extent of anxiety, number and duration of freezing, total distance moved and swimming velocity and biochemical parameters were evaluated viz; dopamine, catalase, glutathione, super oxide dismutase, nitrite (NO) concentration, gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) levels, lipid peroxidation (TBARS), catalase activity, myeloperoxidase activity (MPO). Statistical analysis was done using GraphPad prism software using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test. A significant (* $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$) reduction in test drug Flax Lignan in muscle rigidity and increased locomotor activity was observed, when compared with disease group. Brain neurotransmitter levels of antioxidant ($p \leq 0.01$) were increased and oxidative stress ($p \leq 0.01$) was reduced to that of the standard drug Selegiline. From above studies it can be concluded that ethanoic extract of flax lignan (EEFL) exhibits significant anti-parkinsonism activity in MPTP and rotenone model in mouse and zebrafish respectively.

INTRODUCTION

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Neurotoxicity is a term that defines damage to the nervous system caused due to exposure to chemicals or toxins. When regular exposure to a substance, called neurotoxin occurs, it causes disruption of the normal activity of neurons in the brain leading to cell death of nervous tissue, therefore the term 'neuro'- neuron, 'toxicity'- damage. The causative factors leading to neurotoxicity are, viz; genetic defects, trauma, mental pressure, different simultaneous disease conditions, environmental pollutants, and heavy metals^[1]. The neurotoxic term is used to depict a substance, condition or state that harms the nervous system or brain, usually by destroying neurons. The some of the most common naturally occurring brain toxins are β amyloid ($A\beta$), glutamate and oxygen radicals & when they are present in high dosage they may lead to neurotoxicity and programmed cell death i.e. apoptosis. Excitotoxicity has substantial cellular specificity and, in most cases, is mediated by glutamate receptors. On average, NMDA receptors activation may be able to trigger lethal injury more rapidly than AMPA or kainate receptor activation, perhaps reflecting a greater ability to induce calcium influx and subsequent cellular calcium overload. It is possible that excitotoxicity death may share some mechanisms with other forms of neuronal death^[2]. In current scenario, the etiology of Parkinson's disease is still not clearly understood. Evidences suggest certain causes of neurotoxicity some of the cause of Parkinson's disease is due to: massive oxidative stress leading to the formation of free radical, excessive stimulation of NMDAR leading to excitotoxicity in the central nervous system (CNS) correlated with neuronal cell death. In a review by de Lau and Breteler in 2006, it was reported that an estimated 10 million people in the world (i.e., approximately 0.3% of the world population) and 1% of those above 60 years are found to be affected with PD^[3]. In a door-to-door survey done

in Bangalore district in South Karnataka in India in 2004, the prevalence rate of Parkinsonism was found to be 33 per 100,000 (crude prevalence) and 76 per 100,000 (age adjusted)^[4]. Rural population had a higher prevalence compared to the urban population (41 vs 14). But it was less compared to other highly prevalent neurological disorders such as headache, epilepsy, stroke, and mental retardation. From a survey in Kolkata in 2006, the prevalence of Parkinsonism was found to be 45.82 per 100,000^[5]. In the state of Kashmir^[6], the prevalence was 14.1 per 100,000, while the age adjusted prevalence was 134 per 100,000. A survey, done in Parsi community in Mumbai, a small stable community^[7] showed a prevalence of 192 per 100,000, which was higher compared to rest of the population. In a surveillance in old age homes in a Bangalore there was very high prevalence of 17.6% (109/612 residents) of Parkinsonism^[8]. Currently, no therapeutic intervention can modify disease progression in PD, and dopamine replacement therapy and levodopa remain the gold-standard treatments^[9]. The therapeutic needs of the patient evolve as the disease progresses, and pharmacological or neuromodulatory device-aided therapies are often implemented to manage motor complications in the more advanced phases. Focusing on two main priorities: improving strategies for symptomatic treatment and developing biological therapies that target the disease mechanisms becomes an important aspect for future management of PD that requires the continued use of medications which can alleviate symptomatic manifestations while agents with potential disease-modifying properties are required to be explored^[10]. The said research was undertaken with the objective of the present study was to evaluate the neuroprotective activity of natural polyphenols (Flax Lignan) against Parkinson's disease. Evaluation of anti-Parkinson's activity of polyphenols (Flax Lignan)^[11] using in-vitro, viz; metal chelation assay, nitric

oxide scavenging assays and in-vivo models viz; 1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine (MPTP) mouse model^[12] and rotenone model using zebra fish^[13] was performed. Various behavioral parameters like, muscle grip strength, locomotor activity, muscle rigidity, complete immobility, extent of anxiety, number and duration of freezing, total distance moved and swimming velocity and biochemical parameters were evaluated viz; dopamine, catalase, glutathione, super oxide dismutase, nitrite (NO) concentration, gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) levels, lipid peroxidation (TBARs), catalase activity, myeloperoxidase activity (MPO). Statistical analysis was done using GraphPad prism software using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test. A significant (* $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$) reduction in test drug Flax Lignan in muscle rigidity and increased locomotor activity was observed, when compared with disease group. Brain neurotransmitter levels of antioxidant ($p \leq 0.01$) were increased and oxidative stress ($p \leq 0.01$) was reduced to that of the standard drug Selegiline. From above studies it can be concluded that ethanolic extract of flax lignan (EEFL) exhibits significant anti-parkinsonism activity in MPTP and rotenone model in mouse and zebrafish respectively.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Drugs and Chemicals

Disease inducing chemical MPTP and Rotenone was procured from the company Sigma Aldrich. Standard drug Selegiline was (gift sample obtained from Ranbaxy Research Laboratories, Gurgaon, India) Flax lignin seeds were procured from Ayurveda store and ethanolic extract of flax lignan (EEFL) was prepared. Protocol was submitted for approval to IAEC committee was approved having Protocol no PCOL/IAEC/2019/09 (mice) & PZEB/IAEC/2019/07 (For zebrafish) of Dr.L.H.Hiranandani College of Pharmacy, Ulhasnagar-3.40 Swiss albino mice (20-25g) were

purchased from Bombay veterinary college, Parel, Mumbai- Maharashtra 400012. The animals were brought & acclimatized in animal house under standard husbandry conditions, i.e. room temperature of $24 \pm 1^\circ \text{C}$, relative humidity 45-55% and 12:12 hr. light/dark cycle. The animals were housed in standard propylene cages with wire mesh top and husk as bedding. The animals will have free access for food and water supplied ad libitum under strict hygienic condition. Each experimental group had separate set of animals and care was taken to ensure that animals used for one response were not employed elsewhere. The adult wild zebra fish of 0.5 to 1g was procured from Vikrant aqua culture, Bandra. The fishes were brought to Dr L. H. Hiranandani College of Pharmacy, Opposite to Ulhasnagar Railway Station, Chm Campus, Ulhasnagar -03. The zebra fishes were brought to zebrafish facility, M.pharm Pharmacology laboratory. Zebra fishes were acclimatized in Zebrafish facility located in M.Pharm Pharmacology laboratory under standard husbandry conditions, i.e, temperature of 28°C , optimum pH 7-8, Conductivity of 0.25ppt to 0.75 ppt & 14: 10 hr light/dark cycle.

Experimental Method:

Authentication of Flax Seeds:

Dried *Flax seeds* were procured from Govind Ayurved Bhavan, Dadar (W). The dried powder of flax seeds was authenticated from former HOD Botany of Khalsa College, Matunga, Dr. Harshad M. Pandit, PhD (Botany), Andheri west, Mumbai 400058. (Specimen number **rds p 05530918**.) The dried powders were used for further research work.

Chemical profiling of polyphenol (Flax Lignan)

Chemical profiling of polyphenol: Flaxseed procured from an organic store was cleaned to remove the impurities present in them. The seeds were grounded to a fine powder using a mixer. The resulting flax seed powder was then stored in an air tight container and utilized.

Phytochemical screening was carried out to identify the major natural chemical groups such as tannins, saponins, flavonoids, phenols, terpenoids, alkaloids, glycosides, cardiac glycosides, coumarins and steroids. Estimation of total phenol content test was performed.

3.3. Extraction and purification of lignans from Flaxseed using suitable solvent.

Preparation of defatted flaxseed powder, extraction of lignans from defatted flaxseed powder, lignans extraction procedure was done using ethanol and then lignan compound was separated using hydrolyzing agent, Separation & Purification, then confirmation Lignans by TLC was done.

In-vitro Studies

In-vitro metal chelation assay:

The percentage metal chelating activity was determined by comparing the results of purified Ethanolic Extract of Flax lignan (EEFL) with those of standard EDTA. The result was expressed as IC₅₀ value that is the concentration of EEFL required for 50% inhibition of free ferrous ions.

Antioxidant activity: Nitric oxide scavenging assay

In the in vitro Nitric oxide model, ethanol extracted compound of flax Lignan (EEFL) and Sinigrin showed promising nitric oxide scavenging effect.

In-vivo Studies

1. MPTP induced Parkinson's disease in mice model

Parkinson's disease was induced in 40 mice with MPTP (30mg/kg i.p.); treated with standard Selegiline (10mg/kg s.c.), test group (EEFL 400mg/kg) for 7 days and tested for behavioral parameters on 0 day, 3rd, 5th and 7th day of treatment.

Behavioural parameters evaluated were as follows:

- Locomotor activity by actophotometer
- Motor rigidity by horizontal bar test,

In-vivo estimation of biochemical parameters: On 8th day of in-vivo study, animals were sacrificed, their brains were isolated and following estimations were done.

- Estimation of dopamine
- Estimation of catalase
- Estimation of glutathione
- Estimation of Superoxide dismutases (SOD)

Statistical analysis: The result of neuroprotectant and anti-parkinson's activity for in vivo model were significantly analyzed in GraphPad prism software using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test.

RESULT & CONCLUSION:

Behavioural Parameters Evaluated:

Were observed on 0, 3rd, 5th, 7th day of main study.

1. a. Locomotor activity by Actophotometer

Table no.1.a: Locomotor activity using Actophotometer.

Day Groups	0	3	5	7
	Score of Locomotor activity (Counts/5min)			
Vehicle (1% CMC)	175.5± 8.40	174.5± 11.20	176.16±8.576	184± 14.6
Disease control (MSG 2g/kg)	181.83± 2.00*	107.16±6.63*	97.33±4.24*	76±4.50*
Standard (Selegiline 10mg/kg)	182.33± 14.11**	169.16± 11.69**	161.5±4.12**	157.16 ±3.24**
EEFL (400mg/kg)	179.66± 16.86**	152.33± 12.28**	150.83± 12.41**	146.33± 11.06**

Figure.1.a: Locomotor activity using Actophotometer

Values were expressed as Mean \pm SEM for 6 rats in each group. Significance was determined by One- way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s multiple comparison test’s * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, when compared with disease group. Actophotometer score was found to be increased in groups

administered with EEFL then Standard Seligiline when compared with disease group. Hence it can be concluded that may help in improving locomotor activity in Parkinson’s disease.

1. b. Horizontal bar test

Table no 1.b: Horizontal bar test

Day Groups	0	3	5	7
	Fall of time (Sec)			
Vehicle (1% CMC)	19.33 \pm 2.74	19.67 \pm 2.77	19.87 \pm 1.58	20 \pm 2.14
Disease control (MSG 2g/kg)	10.33 \pm 2.06*	9.5 \pm 1.54*	8.33 \pm 1.96*	4.83 \pm 0.95*
Standard (Seligiline 10mg/kg)	18.45 \pm 2.90**	16.66 \pm 1.47**	16.83 \pm 1.40**	20.33 \pm 1.28**
EEFL (400mg/kg)	17.06 \pm 2.90**	12.33 \pm 2.46**	12.83 \pm 1.20**	14.33 \pm 2.96**

Figure no.1.b: Horizontal bar test

Values were expressed as Mean \pm SEM for 6 rats in each group. Significance was determined by One- way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s multiple comparison test’s * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, when compared with disease group. Fall off time in Horizontal bar test was found to be increased in groups administered with EEFL more significantly then Standard Selegiline when compared with MPTP disease group. Hence it can be concluded

that may help in improving muscle rigidity- a symptom in Parkinson’s disease.

c. Hang Test:

Table no 1.c: Horizontal bar test

Day Groups	0	3	5	7
	Fall of time (Sec)			
Vehicle (1% CMC)	17.83± 3.55	16± 2.33	19± 2.9	21.33± 3.14
Disease control (MSG 2g/kg)	18.17± 2.67*	6± 1.18*	6± 1.07*	5± 0.93*
Standard (Seligiline 10mg/kg)	18.5± 0.99**	15.67± 1.76**	16.83± 2.01**	18.17± 2.83**
EEFL (400mg/kg)	18± 1.67**	12.5 ± 1.33**	16.33± 2.04**	17.5 ± 2.92**

Figure no 1.c: Hang test

Values were expressed as Mean ± SEM for 6 rats in each group. Significance was determined by One- way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s multiple comparison test’s * p≤0.05, ** p≤0.01, when compared with disease group. Fall off time in Hang test was found to be increased in groups

administered with EEFL more significantly than Standard Selegiline when compared with MPTP disease group than disease. Hence it can be concluded that may help in improving neuromuscular strength in Parkinson’s disease

Biochemical Parameters:

Table no 1.d: Biochemical Estimations

Groups	Glutathione (µg/mg protein)	Dopamine (mg/g protein)	Catalase µmoles/g tissue
Vehicle (1% CMC)	25.25± 0.97	4.40± 0.62	4.75± 0.63
MPTP 2g/kg)	7.00± 0.33**	1.99± 0.70**	1.24± 0.78*
(Seligiline 10mg/kg)	15.94± 0.41**	3.59± 0.05**	3.25± 0.98**
EEFL (400mg/kg)	21.58± 0.940***	3.64± 0.01**	4.67± 1.98**

Figure no.1.d: GSH Level

Values were expressed as Mean \pm SEM for 6 rats in each group. Significance was determined by One- way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test's ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$, when compared with disease group. Antioxidant Glutathione was found to be more in groups

administered with EEFL then Standard Selegiline when compared with disease group. Hence it can be concluded that increase in Glutathione may help in improving symptoms of Parkinson's disease.

Figure no.1.e: Dopamine Level

Values were expressed as Mean \pm SEM for 6 rats in each group. Significance was determined by One way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test's ** $p \leq 0.01$, when compared with disease group. Dopamine was found to be more in

EEFL when compared with disease group. Hence it can be concluded that increase in dopamine may help in improving symptoms of Parkinson's disease.

Figure no.1.f: Catalase Level

Values were expressed as Mean \pm SEM for 6 rats in each group. Significance was determined by One- way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test's * $p \leq 0.001$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, when compared with disease group. Antioxidant Catalase was found to be more in groups administered with EEFL when compared with disease group. Hence it can be concluded that increase in catalase may help in improving symptoms of Parkinson's disease.

Hcl (0.03/ μ gML) , EEFL(0.075 μ g/ ML) & (0.3 μ g/ML) for 72 hours and were tested for behavioral parameters after 72 hours of treatment

Following Behavioural parameter were evaluated:

1. Latency to travel from one point to other
2. Time spent near bottom of the
3. Complete cataleptic time
4. Total distance moved & swimming velocity
5. Number of duration of freezing episode
6. Examination tank was used for evaluation of behavioural parameters.

2. Rotenone Induced Parkinson's Disease in Zebra Fish Model

Parkinson's disease was induced in zebra fishes with rotenone (3pg/ml) ;treated with Seligiline

Figure 2.a. Examination Tank^[1]

Experimental Work:

Table no.2.a: Details of Fish

Animals	Details
Species	Zebrafish
Strain	Adult wild type
Weight	0.5 – 1g
Gender	Either sex
No of fishes	40

Fish conditions: The adult wild zebra fish of 0.5 to 1g was procured from Vikrant aqua culture, Bandra. The fishes were brought to Dr L. H.

Hiranandani College of Pharmacy, Opposite to Ulhasnagar Railway Station, Chm Campus, Ulhasnagar -03. The zebra fishes were brought to zebrafish facility, M.pharm Pharmacology laboratory. Zebra fishes were acclimatized in Zebrafish facility located in M.Pharm Pharmacology laboratory under standard husbandary conditions, i.e., temperature of 28° C, optimum pH 7-8, Conductivity of 0.25ppt to 0.75 ppt & 14: 10 hr light/dark cycle.

Table no. 2.b: Study design

Group	Treatment	No. of fishes
Vehicle	10% DMSO	8
Disease	Rotenone 3pg/ml	8
Standard	Selegiline 0.03µg/ml	8
Test Drug	EEFL 0.075µg/ml	8

Preparation Of Drugs:

The dose of EEFL was prepared by suspending in DMSO. Dose of Selegiline was prepared by suspending in water. Vehicle containing 10% DMSO in water was used as control.

Induction to Parkinsons disease:

Induction of Parkinsons disease was done by exposure of fishes to rotenone at the dose of 3pg/ml in water once daily for 72 hours for 30 mins.

Dosing schedules:

For Control: DMSO

Zebra fishes were exposed to Rotenone for 30 mins. then transferred to fresh water for 15

minutes. Zebra fishes were exposed to 10% DMSO for 30 minutes. Transfer to fresh water for 15 minutes.

For Standard: Seligiline

Zebra fishes were exposed to Rotenone for 30 minutes. then transferred to fresh water for 15 minutes. Zebra fishes were exposed to Selegiline for 30 minutes. Transfer to fresh water for 15 minutes.

For Test Drug: EEFL

Zebra fishes were exposed to Rotenone for 30 minutes. Transfer them to fresh water for 15 minutes. Amongst them half zebra fishes were

exposed to EEFL (0.075µg/ml) for 30 minutes, then transfer to fresh water for 15 minutes.

Behavioral parameters:

Total Distance Moved & Swimming Velocity

There is decrease in total distance moved & swimming velocity in Parkinson’s disease. This parameter gave idea about the distance moved during one session in centimetres.

Time Spent Near the Bottom of the Tank:

When they are transferred to new environment, they initially spend more time near of the tank and after some time they come towards the surface, this is attributed towards their exploratory and most often due to anxiety. Thus, the time spend near bottom of the tank gave idea about the extent of anxiety of fish.

Latency to travel from one point to other:

The time taken by the fish to travel from first vertical line to last was calculated at different time. This gave idea about the speed of fish under examination. Catalepsy diminishes the speed of fishes due to rigidity of muscular movement. This

will gave idea about speed of fish under examination.

Complete Cataleptic Time:

Time for which the fish did not move at all i.e. the time for which the fish remained completely immobile during examination period at various time intervals was measured.

Number of Duration of Freezing Episodes:

This parameter gives an idea about total absence in the movement of fishes.

Statistical Analysis:

Results were statistically analysed using ANOVA. All the groups were compared with disease control group.

RESULT & CONCLUSION:

Results were obtained by analyzing values of parameters as Mean± SEM and determining significant difference in group by using one way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test.

Following behavioural parameters were observed

- Number of freezing episodes

Table no 2.c: Number of freezing episodes

Time interval (min)	0	15	30	45	60
	Number of freezing episodes				
Control	0	0	0	0	0
Rotenone	2 ± 0.422**	1.88 ± 0.29**	1.5 ± 0.19**	1.5 ± 0.18**	1.25 ± 0.41**
Selegiline	0	0	0	0	0
EEFL (0.075 µg/ml)	0	0	0	0	0
EEFL (0.3 µg/ml)	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 2.b: Number of freezing episodes

Values were expressed as Mean ± SEM for 8 zebrafish in each group. Significance determined was ** p≤0.01, when compared with disease group. Number of freezing episodes were absent in group administered with EEFL and Selegiline as compared to disease control. Hence it can be

concluded that Dyskinesia –a symptom of PD was improved by significantly by EEFL as then Selegiline as compared to Rotenone treated group.

• **Duration of freezing episodes**

Table no 2.d : Duration of freezing episodes

Time interval (min)	0	15	30	45	60
Groups	Time in seconds				
Control	0	0	0	0	0
Rotenone	8.16 ± 1.09***	2.38 ± 0.26***	2.12 ± 0.35***	2.12 ± 0.22***	1.25 ± 2.56***
Selegiline	0	0	0	0	0
EEFL (0.075 µg/ml)	0	0	0	0	0
EEFL (0.030 µg/ml)	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 2.c: Duration of freezing episodes

Values were expressed as Mean ± SEM for 8 zebrafish in each group. Significance determined was *** p≤0.001, when compared with disease group. Duration of freezing episodes were absent in group administered with EEFL and Selegiline as

compared to disease control. Hence it can be concluded that Dyskinesia –a symptom of PD was improved by the EEFL.

• **Complete cataleptic time**

Table no 2.e: Complete cataleptic time

Time interval (min)	0	15	30	45	60
Groups	Time in seconds				
Control	0	0	0	0	0
Rotenone	13.75 ± 2.39**	9.12 ± 0.47**	8.75 ± 0.72**	7.87 ± 0.71**	4 ± 1.34**
Selegiline	0	0	0	0	0
EEFL (0.075 µg/ml)	0	0	0	0	0
EEFL (0.030µg/ml)	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 2.d: Complete cataleptic time

Values were expressed as Mean ± SEM for 8 zebrafish in each group. Significance determined was, ** p≤0.01, when compared with disease group. Complete cataleptic time was absent in group administered with EECC as compared to

disease control. Hence it can be concluded that complete immobility –a symptom of PD was improved by the EEFL.

• **Time spent near the bottom of the tank**

Table no. 2.f: Time spent near the bottom of the tank

Time interval (min) Groups	0	15	30	45	60
	Time in seconds				
Control	7.35± 1.72	18.5± 3.53	20.5 ± 2.45	19.5 ± 2.31	14.88 ± 4.74
Rotenone	2.25 ± 1.20*	12 ± 1.70*	13.37± 0.88*	7.5 ± 0.77*	10.62 ± 1.67*
Selegiline	5.75 ± 0.55*	14.87 ± 1.368*	15.87 ± 2.27*	16.62 ± 1.87*	11 ± 2.33*
EEFL (0.075 µg/ml)	7.37 ± 2.31**	14.25 ± 2.83**	11.62± 2.90**	13.87 ± 1.51**	8.25 ± 1.64**
EEFL (0.030 µg/ml)	12.37 ± 2.52**	19.87± 3.33**	16.37 ± 2.67**	9.37 ± 1.05**	12.38 ± 3.46**

Figure 2.e: Time spent near the bottom of the tank

Values were expressed as Mean ± SEM for 8 zebrafish in each group. Significance was determined by One way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s multiple comparison test’s* p≤0.05, ** p≤0.01, when compared with disease group. Time spent near the bottom of the tank was more in

group administered with EEFL as compared to disease control i.e. midline crossing was more in test group than disease. Hence it can be concluded that anxiety –a symptom of PD was improved by the EEFL.

Latency to travel from one point to another

Table no.2.g. Latency to travel from one point to another

Time interval (min) Groups	0	15	30	45	60
	Time in seconds				
Vehicle 10% DMSO	6.12± 1.25	4.25± 0.37	8.38 ± 1.49	4.62 ± 0.93	8.25 ± 1.13
Rotenone (3pg/ml)	91.62± 14.16**	10.25 ± 1.48**	8 ± 0.55**	11.25 ± 0.59**	.75 ± 0.89**
ligiline (0.03 µg/ml)	7.62± 1.99***	7.12 ± 1.18***	7 ± 0.82***	7.25 ± 1.03***	8.13 ± 1.14***
EEFL (0.075 µg/ml)	8.75± 1.31**	7.87 ± 0.71**	10.12 ± 1.55**	6.12 ± 0.85**	6.62 ± 6.62**

EEFL (0.03 µg/ml)	7.87 ± 0.61**	5.13 ± 0.29**	6.63 ± 0.96**	5.75 ± 1.14**	4.37 ± 0.70**
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Figure.2.f: Latency to travel from one point to another

Values were expressed as Mean ± SEM for 8 zebrafish in each group. Significance was determined by One way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s multiple comparison test’s ** p≤0.01, *** p≤0.001, when compared with disease group. Latency to travel from one point to another

decreased in group administered with EEFL as compared to disease control. Hence it can be concluded that muscle rigidity –a symptom of PD was improved by the EEFL.

• **Total distance moved**

Table no.2.g : Total distance moved

Time interval (min) Groups	0	15	30	45	60
	Distance moved in cm				
Vehicle 10% DMSO	549.75 ± 35.89	592.5 ± 70.29	618.75 ± 58.26	622.5 ± 26.14	616.5 ± 23.53
Rotenone (3pg/ml)	70.5 ± 29.23*	312 ± 16.62*	303 ± 23.91*	311.25 ± 9.65*	343.5 ± 15.94*
Seligiline (0.03 µg/ml)	541.75 ± 45.32***	546 ± 23.97***	458.25 ± 21.92***	551.25 ± 28.03***	624.25 ± 22.01***
EEFL (0.075µg/ml)	501 ± 43.01***	435 ± 29.39***	420 ± 47.67***	537.75 ± 33.03***	612.60 ± 22.98***
EEFL (0.03µg/ml)	509.25 ± 22.49***	546.75 ± 64.56***	518.25 ± 19.24***	555.75 ± 23.62***	694.75 ± 19.68***

Figure.2.g : Total distance moved

Values were expressed as Mean ± SEM for 8 zebrafish in each group. Significance was determined by One way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s multiple comparison test’s * p≤0.05, *** p≤0.001, when compared with disease group.

Total distance moved by zebrafish was increased in group administered with EEFL as compared to disease control. Hence it can be concluded that bradykinesia –a symptom of PD was improved by the EEFL.

• **Swimming velocity**

Table no.2.h: Swimming velocity

Time interval (min) Groups	0	15	30	45	60
	Velocity (cm/s)				
Vehicle 10% DMSO	4.58 ± 0.29	4.9 ± 0.59	5.15 ± 0.48	5.19 ± 0.22	5.13 ± 0.19
Rotenone (3pg/ml)	0.58 ± 0.24*	2.64 ± 0.13*	2.56 ± 0.20*	2.63 ± 0.07*	2.86 ± 0.13*
Seligiline (0.03 µg/ml)	4.68 ± 0.37***	4.55 ± 0.19***	4.81 ± 0.18***	4.63 ± 0.25***	4.96 ± 0.18***
EEFL (0.075µg/ml)	4.22 ± 0.41***	4.12 ± 0.66***	3.5 ± 0.39***	4.48 ± 0.27***	5.08 ± 0.18***
EEFL (0.03µg/ml)	4.24 ± 0.18***	4.55 ± 0.53***	4.31 ± 0.16***	4.63 ± 0.19***	4.96 ± 0.16***

Figure 2.h.Swimming velocity

Values were expressed as Mean ± SEM for 8 zebrafish in each group. Significance was determined by One way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test's * $p \leq 0.05$, *** $p \leq 0.001$, when compared with disease group. Swimming velocity of zebrafish was increased in group administered with EEFL as compared to disease control. Hence it can be concluded that bradykinesia –a symptom of PD was improved by the EEFL.

CONCLUSION:

In the above research animal models were used which are pivotal for understanding the mechanism of neuroprotection and anti-Parkinsonian activity and development of effective therapy for its optimal management. Oxidative stress is a major player in the pathology of neurodegenerative disorders. The relationship between oxidative stress and neuronal death has been extensively investigated. Oxidative stress generated as a result of mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative metabolism of DA plays an important role in the PD pathogenesis [15].

Excitotoxicity defined as cell death resulting from the toxic actions of excitatory amino acids. Excessive activation of glutamate receptors by excitatory amino acids leads to a number of deleterious consequences, including impairment of calcium buffering, generation of free radicals, activation of the mitochondrial permeability transition and secondary excitotoxicity^[16]. The evaluation of neuroprotection in humans is complex because most of the stimuli required to induce neuronal damage produce irreversible damage. Drug development intended for humans require the demonstration of safety and efficacy in animal models. To reach at a conclusive result and before using it on human beings, the animal study is necessary for dose interpolation for human beings and safety data. Neuroprotection refers to the strategies and relative mechanisms able to defend the central nervous system (CNS) against neuronal injury due to both acute (e.g. stroke or trauma) and chronic neurodegenerative disorders (e.g. Alzheimer's disease, AD, and Parkinson's disease, PD). Neuroprotection is a broad term to

cover any therapeutic strategy to prevent nerve cells called neurons from dying, and it usually involves an intervention, either a drug or treatment. The goal of neuroprotection is to limit neuronal dysfunction after injury and attempt to maintain the possible integrity of cellular interactions in the brain resulting in undisturbed neural function. These products may be of various kinds and can be classified as free radical scavengers, anti-excitotoxic agents, apoptosis inhibitors, neurotrophic factors etc [17]. Kovacsova M. *et.al.* 2014 reported Natural polyphenols have been reported to exert beneficial effects in preventing cardiovascular diseases but their neuroprotective mechanisms were studied much less. They focused on biochemical pathways and molecular neuroprotective mechanisms of natural polyphenols in the brain particularly; the evidence that antioxidant activity, mainly inhibition of the NADPH oxidase and subsequent reactive oxygen species generation; a balance in NO production from different NO synthase isoforms; reduction of neuroinflammation via attenuation of the release of cytokines and downregulation of the pro-inflammatory transcription factors; and the potential to modulate signalling pathways such as mitogen-activated protein kinase cascade and cAMP response element-binding protein are responsible for the neuroprotective actions of different natural polyphenols [18]. Yacoubian T. *et.al.* 2009 reported that Neuroprotection in PD remains an important but elusive goal. A successful neuroprotective treatment could transform PD from a relentlessly progressive and disabling disease to a problem that can be managed with only a modest effect on quality of life. Currently, there are no treatments that are clearly established as neuroprotective in PD, and the discovery of such treatments is an important goal of much work in the field [19]. Natural polyphenols have been reported to exert beneficial effects in preventing cardiovascular diseases but their

neuroprotective mechanisms were studied much less. The polyphenols a chemical widespread within the plant kingdoms, has antioxidant, antiinfectious, and antitumor activities. The neuroprotective actions of polyphenols against N-methyl-d-aspartate (NMDA) investigated in primary cultured cortical neurons by MTT assay are reported in invitro studies [20]. The neuroprotective actions of FLL against N-methyl-d-aspartate (NMDA) are investigated in primary cultured cortical neurons by MTT assay. The expression levels of proteins related to apoptosis and GluN2-containing receptor were detected by Western blot analysis. Intracellular Ca^{2+} was measured under a confocal laser scanning microscope [21]. Test compound Ethanolic Extract of Flax Lignan (EEFL) was selected for favorable physical and chemical properties and its ability to cross the blood brain barrier make it a suitable candidate as a potential treatment approach of neuroprotection in Parkinson's disease. MPTP is considered as the gold standard for toxin based Parkinson Disease models because, it can easily cross the blood brain barrier and where it is taken up by glial cells and metabolized to form 1-methyl-4-phenyl pyridinium (MPP+) by monoamine oxidase-B. Released MPP+ is selectively taken up into dopaminergic neurons by dopamine transporters (DAT) and causing mitochondrial dysfunction, Excitotoxicity, oxidative stress which finally induces apoptosis leads to damage to dopaminergic neurons [22]. Selegiline (Standard) pretreatment can protect neurons against a variety of neurotoxins, such as 1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6 tetrahydropyridine (MPTP), 6-hydroxydopamine, N-(2-chloroethyl)-N-ethyl-2-bromobenzylamine (DSP-4), methyl-beta-acetoxyethyl-2-chloroethylamine (AF64A), and 5,6-dihydroxyserotonin, which damage dopaminergic, adrenergic, cholinergic, and serotonergic neurons, respectively. Selegiline produces an amphetamine-like effect, enhances the release of

dopamine, and blocks the reuptake of dopamine. Selegiline reduces the production of oxidative radicals, up-regulates superoxide dismutase and catalase, and suppresses nonenzymatic and iron-catalyzed autooxidation of dopamine. Also causes over activation of NMDA receptor exerts excitotoxicity. Over activation of NMDA along with other glutamate / glycine receptors disturb the calcium homeostasis, which is the key mediator if glutamate – induced excitotoxicity neuronal damage. Selegiline, diminishes potentiation of the NMDA receptors by the polyamine binding site^[23] hence Selegiline was used as standard. Rotenone generates an experimental animal model of Parkinson disease that Mimics and elicits Parkinson like symptoms such as muscular rigidity, bradykinesia, postural instability, unsteady gait and sleep disturbances. Due to its high lipophilicity, rotenone can readily cross Blood brain barrier and enter all cells without being dependent on specific transporter. Application of low doses of rotenone in vitro and in vivo have been shown to affect many of the mechanisms involved in Pathogenesis of Parkinson Disease, like altered calcium signalling, induction of oxidative stress and apoptosis, loss of tyrosine hydroxylase, proteasomal dysfunction, nigral iron accumulation. Since rotenone, a complex I inhibitor, can cause many of the pathological features of PD in rats and complex I dysfunction has been associated with PD in humans. Rotenone used as agent for PD model due to inhibit mitochondrial complex I (c-I), decreasing endogenous antioxidants and generating oxidative stress from complexes I and III (c I, c III, respectively) which leads to oxidation of macromolecules. Additionally, cytochrome c (Cyt c) is released from the intermitochondrial space, activating caspase signaling and subsequent apoptotic cell death^[24]. Zebrafish is becoming an increasingly attractive model organism for understanding biology and developing

therapeutics, because as a vertebrate, it shares considerable similarity with mammals in both genetic compositions and tissue/organ structures, and yet remains accessible to high throughput phenotype-based genetic and small molecule compound screening. Zebrafish models have significantly contributed to our understanding of vertebrate development and, more recently, human disease^[24]. In the present study, results obtained from MPTP induced Parkinson's disease in mice showed improvement in locomotor activity, decrease in muscle rigidity, neuromuscular strength was improved in Parkinson's disease when treated with Ethanolic extract of flax lignan (EEFL) as compared to standard drug Selegiline and disease group induced with Parkinson's disease using MPTP. Biochemical estimations done on 8th day of in-vivo study sacrificed animals brains, it was observed increase in glutathione activity, also prominent restoring activity of dopamine levels and catalase levels were observed. Rotenone is a pesticide, insecticide, etc. Application of low doses of rotenone in vivo have been shown to affect many of the mechanisms involved in pathogenesis of pd, such as altered calcium signalling, induction of oxidative stress and apoptosis, loss of tyrosine hydroxylase nigral iron accumulation formation of fibrillary cytoplasmic inclusions. Other studies have also shown that exposure to Rotenone induced behavioural and motor deficits, which are similar to human PD, including muscle rigidity, bradykinesia, postural instability, unsteady gaits and sleep disturbances. In Rotenone model of Zebra fish for Parkinson's disease the study of behavioral parameters like latency to travel from one point to another, time spent near the bottom of tank, complete immobility time, erratic swimming were found to be increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) in toxic control group and as compared to vehicle control group, experimental drug group, standard control group, the parameters were found to be

decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$). Ethanol extract of flax lignan (EEFL) neuroprotective activity against oxidative stress and excitotoxicity model in Parkinson's disease via NMDA antagonistic property. Patients with PD usually present with features indicative of degeneration of nigrostriatal pathways. A useful clinical definition for PD is "asymmetric onset of an akinetic (bradykinetic) rigid syndrome with resting tremor and a good response to levodopa". When applied by neurologists with an interest in movement disorders, this definition has a pathological correlation exceeding 98%.⁴ The use of dopaminergic drugs improves motor function, significantly reduces both the morbidity and mortality of PD, and improves quality of life. Levodopa remains the drug most commonly used in PD. It is very effective in improving bradykinesia and rigidity, and in practice remains the gold standard against which other drugs are judged. Some studies, predominantly in vitro, have suggested that levodopa. Current therapy options for PD remain focussed on the symptomatic improvement of motor features related predominantly to loss of dopaminergic neurones in the substantia nigra. Such treatment is effective in improving morbidity and mortality^[24]. Thus, the above research is based on the basis where recent insights into the aetiology, pathology, and pathogenesis of PD are providing important opportunities to develop disease modifying therapies that will have an even greater impact on the disease than did the introduction of levodopa

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HOW TO CITE: Rachana Sarawade*, C. D. Upasani, Evaluation of Neuroprotective Effect of Flax Lignan Against Parkinson's Disease in Animal Model, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 1, 337-353. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14606032>

